

Studies of the electro-optic noise in crystalline coatings and cryogenic coating mechanical losses

Satoshi Tanioka,¹ Nicholas Didio,¹ Daniel Vander-Hyde,¹ Elenna Capote,¹
Steven D. Penn,² Stefan W. Ballmer¹

¹ Department of Physics, Syracuse University, Syracuse, New York 13244, USA

² Department of Physics, Hobart William Smith Colleges,
300 Pulteney Street, Geneva, New York 14456, USA

March 2, 2023

Abstract

Thermal noise arising from high-reflective mirror coatings limits the current ground-based gravitational wave detectors. Reducing this coating thermal noise improves the sensitivity of detectors and enriches the scientific outcome of observing runs. We are studying the electro-optic noise in crystalline coatings and coating mechanical losses at cryogenic temperature toward future gravitational wave detectors. Here we report current status of our experiments.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7050589

Introduction

The sensitivity of current ground-based laser interferometric gravitational wave detectors (GWDs) is limited by Brownian thermal noise in amorphous silica and titania-doped tantala coatings at their most sensitive frequency band [1, 2]. Development of low thermal noise mirror coatings plays an important role to improve the sensitivities of future upgraded GWDs.

Power spectral density of coating Brownian thermal noise can be expressed as [3]

$$S(f) \propto \frac{k_B T}{2\pi f} \frac{d}{w} \phi_C, \quad (1)$$

where k_B , T , f , d , w , and ϕ_C are the Boltzmann constant, the temperature, the frequency, the coating thickness, the beam radius, the coating mechanical loss, respectively. Therefore, employing cryogenically cooled mirror or low mechanical loss coatings are effective approaches to improve the sensitivity toward future GWDs.

Crystalline gallium arsenide (GaAs) and aluminum-alloyed gallium arsenide (AlGaAs) coatings (referred to as AlGaAs coatings), which have demonstrated low thermal noise, are one of the coating candidates for future GWDs [4, 5]. While crystalline AlGaAs coatings can reduce thermal noise, they can be susceptible to the coupling from fluctuations in the electric field called electro-optic (EO) noise. In order to investigate the impact of the EO effect in AlGaAs coatings, we have developed an experimental setup using a Fabry-Perot (FP) cavity. From this experiment we set an upper limit on the EO noise which is well below the strain sensitivity of future upgraded GWDs.

Studying coating mechanical losses at cryogenic temperature is vital to understand the origin of coating mechanical losses and to develop low thermal noise coatings at cryogenic temperature. We built a cryogenic gentle nodal suspension (GeNS) to measure the coating mechanical losses at cryogenic temperature. This apparatus enables us to measure the coating mechanical losses at broad temperature range, $\sim 15 - 300$ K.

AlGaAs coating electro-optic effect measurement

When an electric field is applied to a specific material, its refractive index varies depending on this field. This effect is called the electro-optic (EO) effect.

The refractive indices of crystal can be expressed in terms of its index ellipsoid as

$$\frac{x^2}{n_x^2} + \frac{y^2}{n_y^2} + \frac{z^2}{n_z^2} = 1, \quad (2)$$

where n_x , n_y , and n_z are the three principal refractive indices with the crystallographic axes as the optical axes [6]. For the case of zincblende crystals such as GaAs and AlGaAs, the refractive indices are $n_x = n_y = n_z = n_0$. The refractive indices when the electric field is applied to a zincblende crystal can be described as

$$n_{x'} = n_0 + \frac{1}{2}n_0^3r_{41}E, \quad (3)$$

$$n_{y'} = n_0 - \frac{1}{2}n_0^3r_{41}E. \quad (4)$$

where r_{41} represents the electro-optic coefficient, and x' , y' , and z' are the new principal axes when the electric field is applied. Therefore, the fluctuations in the electric field couples to the fluctuations in the refractive indices, hence optical phase. Consequently, when the linear polarization of the beam is aligned to x' or y' axes, the reflected optical phase is perturbed by the EO effect, resulting in equivalent cavity length fluctuations.

It should be noted that x' and y' axes are rotated counterclockwise through an angle 45° with respect to the positive z -axis [6, 7]. For the case of GaAs and AlGaAs, x , and y axes correspond to the [010] or [001], one of the [100] family of directions. x' and y' axes are one of the [011] family of directions. Therefore, the changes of refractive due to the normal electric field are induced in principal axes of the [110] family of directions.

Figure 1 shows the optical layout (Left) and measurement scheme (Right). The FP cavity is composed of two high-reflective mirrors — amorphous coated front mirror and AlGaAs coated end mirror. The AlGaAs coated mirror and electrodes are housed in the same mirror mount made of machinable glass. Each electrode has a hole with 3 mm diameter to pass the beam through. Input beam is linearly polarized, and its polarization can be aligned to the crystal axes of AlGaAs coatings by rotating a $\lambda/2$ plate in front of the FP cavity. The laser frequency is locked to the cavity length by Pound-Drever-Hall (PDH) technique [8]. Cavity length fluctuations induced by the electric field is imprinted on the PDH error signal.

We measure the transfer function from source voltage sent to the electrode to PDH feed back signal as shown in Figure 1. If the source signal V_{in} is much larger than the noises, n_{laser} , n_S , and n_F , the measured transfer function can be expressed as

$$\frac{V_{\text{out}}}{V_{\text{in}}} \approx \frac{FS}{1+G}CEA_2 = \frac{G}{1+G}CE\frac{A_2}{A_1}, \quad (5)$$

Figure 1: Schematic of experimental setup (Left) and equivalent block diagram of measurement scheme (Right). Laser frequency is locked to the cavity length by PDH method. The demodulated signal is filtered by frequency stabilization servo (FSS) and then fed back to the laser PZT through a high-voltage amplifier (HVA). End AlGaAs coating mirror, which is a flat mirror, is placed between two aluminum electrodes which apply the electric field normal to the mirror surface. Voltage is applied to the front electrode through an HVA, and back electrode is grounded. Transfer function from source signal V_{in} to PDH feedback signal V_{out} is measured by using SR785.

where $G \equiv A_1 F S$ is the open-loop gain, and each character corresponds to the transfer function of plant as shown in Figure 1. When G , E , A_1 , and A_2 are known, coupling level of the EO effect, C , can be obtained from Equation 5.

Figure 2 shows the results which were calibrated by measuring G , E , A_1 , and A_2 . Measurements were carried out with three different polarizations — P-, S-, and intermediate (referred to as P&S-) polarizations. The electric field couples to the cavity length through not only the EO effect but also mechanical motion. For instance, the peaks around 11 kHz and 70 kHz, are mechanical resonances of the mirror mount and the AlGaAs coated mirror itself, respectively.

Here we focus on the frequency range 20 – 50 kHz which is free from mechanical resonances. There is a small difference in transfer function between the three polarizations. In principle, the EO effect is induced in $[011]$ and $[0\bar{1}1]$ axes, and does not couple in $[010]$ axis. Therefore, the difference in transfer function between those three polarizations can be attributed to the EO effect in AlGaAs coatings. From the obtained results, the EO effect is smaller than 1.0×10^{-16} m/(V/m).

The measured fluctuations in the electric field next to the test mass in aLIGO is 3×10^{-6} (V/m)/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 100 Hz [9]. Assuming that the level of electric field fluctuations at each test mass is 3×10^{-6} (V/m)/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 100 Hz and there is no correlation between them, the upper limit of the EO effect can be calculated as

$$\frac{2 \times 1.0 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m/(V/m)} \times 3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (V/m)/}\sqrt{\text{Hz}}}{4 \times 10^3 \text{ m}} = 1.5 \times 10^{-25} \text{ 1/}\sqrt{\text{Hz}}. \quad (6)$$

Comparing to the designed sensitivity of upgrade plan of Advanced LIGO (A+), the noise level of the EO effect at 100 Hz is one order of magnitude smaller than that of A+ sensitivity, about 2.0×10^{-24} 1/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ [10]. Therefore, the EO effect in AlGaAs coatings will not be a limiting noise source in future upgrade GWDs. Further characterization is underway to more precisely evaluate the EO effect and the impact on the sensitivity.

Figure 2: Calibrated results.

Cryogenic Gentle Nodal Suspension

Measurement of coating mechanical losses plays an important role in developing low thermal noise coatings for future GWDs. A GeNS is one of the measurement systems which allows us to measure coating mechanical losses [11, 12]. In order to study the coating mechanical losses at cryogenic temperature, we developed an apparatus.

Figure 3 shows the cryogenic GeNS apparatus we developed at Syracuse University. In our setup, GeNS is housed inside the cryostat chamber, which allows us to cool down a sample to about 15 K. This cryogenic GeNS can accommodate either 3 inch or 4 inch sample disk by replacing the sample holders. Mechanical disk modes are excited by applying broadband white noise voltage to the electrodes above the disk. As the pressure is kept below 10^{-6} Torr at cryogenic temperature, damping loss due to residual gas is negligible. Decay of those excited disk modes are probed by an optical lever (OpLev) as shown in Figure 3. A HeNe laser beam is injected into the cryostat chamber and hit the upper surface of the disk. The reflected beam is extracted from the cryostat chamber and impinge on a quadrant photodetector (QPD), and output signals from four segments of QPD are combined to obtain horizontal and vertical beam spot position which is proportional to the angular motion of the disk. The sensitivity coefficient of an OpLev, A_{OpLev} , is expressed as

$$A_{\text{OpLev}} \equiv \frac{\delta P_{\text{diff}}}{\delta \theta} = -2\sqrt{2}D \frac{\bar{P}}{w}, \quad (7)$$

where δP_{diff} , $\delta \theta$, D , \bar{P} , and w are differential QPD signal, angular disk motion, OpLev arm length, beam power on the QPD, and beam size on the QPD, respectively. The arm length of our setup, D , is chosen as 2 m. Two lenses are installed in the input optical system to make the beam size on the QPD about 300 – 400 μm . This enables us to reach a conversion factor from a angular disk motion to

Figure 3: Cryogenic GeNS apparatus. The layout inside the cryostat chamber with 3 inch silicon wafer (Left) and the optical setup (Right). The installed optics consist an optical lever to probe the displacement of the silicon wafer.

normalized QPD signals, A_{OpLev}/\bar{P} , as about $1.5 \times 10^4 \text{ rad}^{-1}$, which is comparable to previous study [12].

Figure 4 shows the obtained mechanical losses of 3 inch silicon wafer. The data is recorded by using a LabView data acquisition code written by the co-author (SP), and then analyzed by a time-domain analysis method [13]. In this measurement, a double side polished high-purity silicon wafer (Ultrasil LLC.) is used which has a diameter of 76.2 mm and a thickness of 0.50 mm. The orientation of wafer is $\langle 100 \rangle$, and its resistivity is more than $10 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}$. Temperature was probed by a temperature sensor attached close to the disk. Below about 150 K, mechanical loss of 681 Hz mode is smaller than 10^{-7} , i.e., Q-value of this mode is larger than 10^7 . Especially, mechanical loss becomes smaller than 10^{-8} around 30 K. This indicates that the extrinsic loss, which hinders us to measure mechanical loss of the sample, is below 10^{-8} . Therefore, our cryogenic GeNS setup has enough sensitivity to measure low mechanical loss samples at cryogenic temperature. On the other hand, as thermoelastic damping of silicon wafer is dominant, the Q-value at room temperature is above 10^5 . This trend is consistent with that of a previous study [14]. It should be noted that larger mechanical losses were observed for modes other than 681 Hz. The cause of this is unknown at this time. Further measurements are ongoing to reveal the origin of this behavior.

Conclusions

We experimentally investigated the noise induced by the EO effect in AlGaAs coatings induced by the fluctuations in the electric field. We set an upper limit on the coupling level of the EO effect in AlGaAs coating, and show that the EO effect will not be a limiting noise source in future upgraded GWDs. In addition, we built a cryogenic GeNS setup to study the coating mechanical losses. This setup enables us to measure coating mechanical losses with either 3 inch or 4 inch sample even at cryogenic temperature about 15 K.

Figure 4: Measured mechanical losses with 3 inch silicon wafer.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by NSF grants PHY-2011723 and PHY-1920023.

References

- [1] G. M. Harry et al. Thermal noise from optical coatings in gravitational wave detectors. *Appl. Opt.*, 45(7):1569–1574, Mar 2006.
- [2] S. Gras and M. Evans. Direct measurement of coating thermal noise in optical resonators. *Phys. Rev. D*, 98:122001, Dec 2018.
- [3] Gregory M Harry, Andri M Gretarsson, Peter R Saulson, Scott E Kittelberger, Steven D Penn, William J Startin, Sheila Rowan, Martin M Fejer, D R M Crooks, Gianpietro Cagnoli, Jim Hough, and Norio Nakagawa. Thermal noise in interferometric gravitational wave detectors due to dielectric optical coatings. *Classical and Quantum Gravity*, 19(5):897–917, feb 2002.
- [4] D. Cole, G et al. Tenfold reduction of brownian noise in high-reflectivity optical coatings. *Nature Photonics*, 7(8):644–650, 2013.
- [5] S. D. Penn et al. Mechanical ringdown studies of large-area substrate-transferred GaAs/AlGaAs crystalline coatings. *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B*, 36(4):C15–C21, Apr 2019.

- [6] Amnon Yariv. *Quantum Electronics (3rd. ed)*. John Wiley & Sons, 1989.
- [7] Susumu Namba. Electro-Optical Effect of Zincblende. *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, 51(1):76–79, Jan 1961.
- [8] R. W. P. Drever, J. L. Hall, F. V. Kowalski, J. Hough, G. M. Ford, A. J. Munley, and H. Ward. Laser phase and frequency stabilization using an optical resonator. *Applied Physics B: Lasers and Optics*, 31(2):97–105, June 1983.
- [9] A. Buikema et al. Sensitivity and performance of the advanced ligo detectors in the third observing run. *Phys. Rev. D*, 102:062003, Sep 2020.
- [10] L. Barsotti et al. The a+ design curve. *LIGO Document: LIGO-T1800042*, 2018.
- [11] E. Cesarini et al. A “gentle” nodal suspension for measurements of the acoustic attenuation in materials. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 80(5):053904, 2009.
- [12] G. Vajente et al. A high throughput instrument to measure mechanical losses in thin film coatings. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 88(7):073901, 2017.
- [13] E. Capote et al. in preparation.
- [14] M. Granata et al. Internal Friction and Young’s Modulus Measurements on SiO₂ and Ta₂O₅ Films Done with an Ultra-High Q Silicon-Wafer Suspension. *Archives of Metallurgy and Materials*, (No 1 March), 2015.